

SYNERGIZING GREEN MARKETING AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY FOR SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENTAL AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

Eze Ifeanyi Michael

Department of Marketing, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria

Abstract:

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) and green marketing adoption is a twin trend that is fast becoming a global tendency amongst world economies, irrespective of socio-economic outlook. This paper pedagogically links the two concepts in the Nigeria business climes and explores, through a panoramic view the rate of adoption of CSR and green marketing in Nigeria. This study adopted an exploratory research design vis-à-vis a qualitative research approach. Based on the findings, this paper posits that corporate social responsibility in the Nigerian context is highly “localized” to reflect realities in the Nigerian socio-cultural space. However, green marketing adoption is near impossible for the average Nigerian organization; this is due in part to the enormous funds necessary for implementation of green marketing strategies in their businesses. This study therefore recommends the setting up of trust fund for companies (especially, small scale business) by government; this would give the companies the opportunity to fully develop and adopt green marketing strategy.

Keywords: Corporate social responsibility; Green marketing adoption; customers; Nigeria

Introduction

In the world of the academia, it is empirically evident that the practice of green marketing amongst businesses have occupied huge scholarly space since it first emerged in the marketing literature landscape around the 1980's (Simbriso, Mntongi & Thabani, 2021; Prothero, 1990; Elkington, 1989; Huxley, 1968; Kotler & Levy 1969; Kotler & Zaltman, 1970; Punitha & Rasdi, 2013; Oko & Agbonifoh, 2014; Amaeshi et al, 2006). Green marketing: a recent coinage in marketing literature is well embedded in the boarder concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR). Although the green marketing concept is new, CSR is old and fully encapsulated in the general objective of marketing role in the society (Kotler

&Levy, 1969; Kotler & Zalthman, 1969). Although, a school of thought believes that a corporation has no social responsibility to its stakeholders except to make profit in a legal way (Friedman, 1970); it should be noted that corporation has enormous responsibilities to its stakeholders through its commitment in improving community wellbeing (Hossain et al, 2014).

In regulating the business environment, government develops rules and regulations to protect the interest of the society. Oftentimes these regulations threaten the primary mandate of business organization which is profit maximization (Okon & Agbonifoh, 2014). It can also affect the organization's corporate objectives of the firm, stakeholders, and members of the public as well as the preservation of the ecological environment and ultimately,

public welfare (Oko & Agbonifoh, 2014). The urge to satisfy the society in this line of thought gave birth to corporate social responsibility (Davis, 1998; Menon & Menon, 1977; Hartimao & Stafford, 1998; Oko & Agbonifoh, 2014). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families, the local community and the society at large (Holme & Walt, 2001). This definition alludes to the fact that there exists a relationship between the environment and the attainment of business objective. Studies agree that a good relationship between business objectives and the environment could lead to improved corporate image and reputation of business (Hardy, 1996; Turban & Greening, 1997), generation of business opportunities and profit (O'Toole, 1991), corporate sustainability, social progress and improved economic environment (Kanji & Chopa, 2010) as well as saving organization from illegalities and convictions (Baucus & Baucus, 1997). Oko & Agbonifoh (2014) suggests the complete optimization of this relationship in favour of the environment and socially responsible activities should form corporate lifestyle of firms. In developed economies such as the United States (USA), firms and businesses have turned from issues relating to corporate social responsibility and green marketing around by becoming "active problem solvers" in issues relating to (Bateman & Snell, 1999; Kilbourne, 1998). Green marketing is one of the ways of addressing the issue of corporate social responsibility (CSR) targeted towards the environment (Amaeshi et al, 2006). The development of green marketing has the objective of minimizing the impact of marketing activities on the natural environment (Punith & Rasdi, 2013). Green marketing is the way to conceive exchange relationship that goes beyond the current needs of the consumers, considering at the same time the social interest in protecting the environment (Chairman & Banegil, 2006). The definition is closer to CSR's definition of maintaining a relationship between the environment and the business. Although in this case, the definition alludes to an exchange relationship, that is, there is a transfer of something of value between the two parties Rahman; Reynolds & Svaren (2011) suggested sustainability in their own view. According to them, green marketing means a business that is operated in a way that decreases waste, is environmentally friendly, saves energy and mostly encourages environmental health and sustainability of the society. However, for (Soonthonsani; 2007), societal satisfaction is the basis of green marketing. According to him, green marketing are acts performed by organizations that are hesitant about the ecology or green problems by offering environmentally friendly goods or services to bring fulfillment among customers and the community. The issue of green marketing is often associated with product-based industry (Runitha & Rasid, 2013) due to its high visibility in terms of manufacturing, handling and removal of raw-materials. Customers demonstrate affirmative intent to buy goods that adopt green practices than preferring the ones that don't (Han & Choi, 2012). Today, green marketing is a buzz word in the business landscape. It has offered comfort to firms to employ as a springboard to execute CSR (Stafaat & Sultan, 2012). In the Nigeria context, CSR is shaped by socio-cultural pressures (Amaeshi et al, 2006). The Nigeria business landscape consists of indigenous companies that are mostly SME's that are privately managed, kin and kith owned and managed firms (Limbs & Fort, 2000; Ahunwan, 2002) and some multinational companies. CSR is practiced by the multi-national companies in Nigeria due to their global visibility and outreach (Amaeshi et al, 2006); Oko & Agbonifoh, 2014). Limbs & Fort (2010) identified three factors that shape business practice in Nigeria; they are ethnicity, language and religion. The philosophy that guides business practice in Nigeria is a communal philosophy of life which is deeply rooted in the concept of extended kinship (Amaeshi, et al, 2006). Historically, the Nigerian business landscape is characterized by "banditry": an initial strategy developed by the colonial firms in their dealing with the Nigerian people, therefore, the use of force is seen as a necessary, mandatory and even normal procedure (Fongere & Solitander, 2009, Soferrio & Sanchez, 2010; Amaeshi, et al, 2016). Nigeria with a per capital income of \$ 390 and life expectancy

of 45 years (World Bank, 2006) do not have a conclusive environment that can favour the adoption, development and growth of CSR concepts and green marketing principles. Little emphasis is placed on CSR waves such as employee relations and consumer protection in Nigeria because, the framework that exist in Nigeria does not give adequate space for perspectives that originates from the stakeholders nor a mindset that is built on socialist model (Amaeshi et al, 2006)

The purpose of CSR in developed economies is to maximize the positive effect of firms on society and minimize the negative impact of these activities on the society (Fanell & Fraedich, 1997). Also, in these developed economics, the consumer and producer are usually socially responsible unlike in developing countries such as Nigeria where consumers lack the knowledge to make informed decisions regarding the purchase, use and disposition of product (Preston & Post 1995; Oko & Agbonifoh, 2014), hence their susceptibility to deception. The thrust of this paper is to find out through a thematic paper review, the rate of adoption of green marketing practice as well as CSR concept in Nigeria with a view to identify whether firms actually embark on them or pay mere lip service to them.

Literature Review Concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

There is scanty literature on the definition of corporate social responsibility (CSR). The term is still at a “pre-paradigmatic phase” (Punitha & Rasdi, 2013), which suggest disagreement amongst scholars regarding the definition of CSR and what its scope is likely to contain (Googins, Manin & Rochlin, 2007). The meaning of the concept is still evolving (Baron 2001; Canoll & Shabana, 2010; Lee, 2008; Secchi, 2007; Punitha & Rasdi, 2013). The EU Green paper on CSR defines it as “a concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interactions with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis. Mc Williams & Siegel (2001) defines CSR from the view point of charity. According to them, CSR are actions that appear to further some common good beyond the interest of the firm and that which is required by law. CSR is the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families, the local community and the society at large (Holme & Walt, 2001).

Corporate social responsibility is defined as “a demonstration of certain responsible behaviour on the part of public and the private [government and business] sectors toward society and the environment (Dirk and Jeremy). In the views of Simbriso et al, 2021), it is a “comprehensive set of policies, practices and programmes that are integrated into business operations, supply chain, and decision-making processes throughout the company”. Posk et al, (1999) on the other hand believes that corporations should be held accountable for their actions especially when the activities of the corporations have adverse effect on the people, communities and environment. This stance is unpopular amongst some scholars who believe that CSR is a cost center which additional cost will jeopardize the effectiveness of an organization (Pinkson & Carroll, 1996; Henderson, 2009).

Carroll (1979) states that social responsibility of business encompasses the economic, legal, ethical and discretionary expectations that society has of organization at a given point in time; the four components (economic, legal, ethical and discretionary) identified here are in line with the thought of Oko and Agbonifoh (2014) that identified these four expectations as the scope of CSR. Economic component refers to business duty of providing a return on savings to owners and stakeholders of the business as well as providing, jobs, good and services to the society (Visser, 2008). Discretionary expectation/ component which is interchangeably called philanthropic component is all about promoting welfare of humans through organization’s engagement in humanitarian or voluntary programmes (Carroll, 1991). This responsibility is seen as obligatory in developed countries and an expected norm in developing countries (Visser, 2008). The legal section suggests performing

business in line with the rules and regulations guiding such endeavors in order to benefit society (Carroll, 1991; Ismaili, 2009; Mullerat & Brennan, 2015).

Ethical component suggest that companies include strategies in their operations that would help sustain the environment (Hiseh 2009; Tsoi, 2010) for future generations. This component goes beyond stated law and relies more on the moral codes of the companies identified by the society. Visser (2008) proposed that these components be used to form the CSR pyramid for developing countries. According to him, the components, although distinct constructs are interrelated to one another and is seen as a unified system. The figure below helps to buttress this point. The globally accepted definition of CSR is primarily based on “Anglo-American” precedence, viewpoint and values (Quasi & O’ Brien, 2000; Kemp, 2000; Chapple&Benneth, 1998; Chapple& Moon, 2005). This trend has encouraged emergent literature on diverse definition of CSR across culture and national boundaries (Orpen, 1987; Benneth, 1998; Qazi& O Brien, 2000; Chapple& Moon, 2005). The literatures show that the practice of CSR has socio-cultural connotations. Chapple& Moon (2005) however suggests that any definition of CSR must be based on the waves, issues and modes of CSR. The waves of CSR are community involvement, socially responsible production processes and socially responsible employee relations. These waves are identified based on the issues they emphasis which include environment, education, employee welfare, health and safety. Modes of CSR are the means for implementation which could be through partnership, philanthropy, foundation and codes.

The definition of CSR in the Nigerian context is not unconnected with the socio-cultural heritage of indigenous firms in Nigeria (Amaeshi, et al, 2006). The Nigeria economy is largely controlled by what Adi (2006) termed “the household economy”. In this sense, the “kinship-network-based” system of business means that in Nigeria business first cater for the interest of the family network members. Philanthropy, which is how CSR is perceived amongst business in Nigeria, goodness and charity are viewed within the moral economy of kin-based solidarity and reciprocity. Aside the socio-cultural heritage of business in Nigeria, the market and regulatory forces in Nigeria is terminally weak and this would ultimately slow the growth of CSR. There is also a low emphasis on waves of CSR such as socially responsible employee relations. In western economies, there are strong market and regulatory mechanism that ensures the growth of CSR. Nigeria also faces numerous socio-economic challenges such as poverty, poor healthcare facilities, poor infrastructural development and poor quality of education. It is with this background that (Amaeshi et al,2006) proposed that CSR in Nigeria should reflects local realities and patterns of need that is targeted at curbing the atypical socio-economic development challenges faced in the country.

Fig 1: CSR pyramid for developing countries

Source: Adapted from Visser (2008) in Punilta&Rosdi, 2013.

Concept of Green Marketing

Conceptually, green marketing havevaried definitions, however, one phenomenon is constant: green marketing is one of the many means corporations use inresponding to the society in terms of performing their corporate social responsibilities. Green marketing is perceived differently by different fields of the marketing discipline. For instance, the American Marketing Association which is the recognized body charged with streamlining marketing thought has three definitions for the concept emanating from three distinct fields of marketing. First, the field of retailing defines green marketing as the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. The second definition is from the marketing fields of social marketing, it perceives green marketing as the development and marketing of product designed to minimize negative effects on the physical environment or improve its quality. Lastly, environmental marketing defines green marketing as the efforts by the organization to produce, promote, package and reclaim product in the manner that is sensitive or responsive to ecological concerns. In this sense, it means that green marketing is holistic in nature and it incorporates production and marketing process (Gbadeyan&Omolekan, 2015). It is a complete overhaul of the whole marketing process (Chan, 2014).

An empirical study of consumers of green products in Benin City show that green marketing is yet to be a popular trend among consumers, in order to correct this, there is a need to improve on appropriate application of effective strategies tailored towards green marketing adoption. In (Amaeshi et al 2006) opinion indigenous firms in Nigeria perceive and practice CSR as corporate philanthropy aimed at addressing socio-economic development challenges in Nigeria. It confirms that CSR is a “localized” and socially embedded construct. In the same light, Punitha&Rasdi (2013) who studied green marketing adoption amongst hotels in Malaysia argues that green marketing is a means used by hotels to execute CSR while it offers a competitive advantage for the hotels in growth and environmental sustainability. On the contrary, Oko&Agbonifoh (2014) study discovered that CSR in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria was poor due to government unwillingness to sacrifice expected high returns on petroleum exploration for the development of the area. They recommend a joint action plan implementation between all participants and stakeholders in the oil business of the Niger Delta region. On the major factors that influence green marketing behaviour amongst adolescence in Hong Kong (Lee, 2008) through a multiple regression analysis discovered social influence as a top predictor of green purchasing behavior of the Hong Kong adolescent. Green marketing is the brainchild to the critical issues of environmentalism that formed the bane of

research in the 1990's. In the decade that was famously referred to as the "Earth decade" (McDaniel & Rylander, 1993), issues of environmental protection and preservation was gained momentum in the business world. Environmental issues are not new although, the coinage "green marketing" is new.

In the 1970's issues regarding the exultation of the customer need and satisfaction (marketing concept) over the improve effect of such exaltation on the environment were raised (Bell and Emery, 1971; Feldman, 1971). Societal marketing concept was then suggested by (Kotler, 1976) to ensure that firms are socially responsible and then consumer wants and satisfaction was then elaborated to include

"Consumer interest", "company requirement" and "societal welfare". In advance economics, especially in the United State of America, environmental concerns that threaten societal welfare include landfills, polluted waters, ozone layer depletion, resources and greenhouse effect (Mc Daniel & Rylander, 1993). In Nigeria, environmental concerns include issues on environmental pollution as a result of waste from product and product packages, global warning, deforestation, desertification and flooding (Gbadeyan&Omolekan, 2015). To be truly successful, corporation must integrate green marketing into the strategic marketing plan of the organization (Mc Daniel & Rylander, 1993). It also provides the company opportunity to co-brand their products into separate lines to show off their "eco-friendliness" (Gbadeyan & Omolekan, 2015). Amidst this benefit of green marketing, in developing economics there still exist a wide gap between understanding and implementation

Evolution of Green Marketing

Green marketing has its root prior to its prominence in late 1980's and early 1990's in the preceding decade of the 70's when the issue of the role of organization in the society gripped the marketing landscape. However, its evolution occurred in three phases (Peattie & Crane, 2005). The first phase was termed "ecological green marketing"; during this time, all marketing activities were directed at helping environmental problems and providing remedies as well (Jaspreet, Jatin, Jogesh & Jupinder, 2012). According to (Lee, 2008), the development of several green products does not automatically translate to positive consumer outcomes such as increased goodwill and increased market share for the organization. Market outcome fell short of the company's expectation (Wong et al, 1996). The euphoria that surrounded the idea of green marketing at that time died suddenly (Peattie & Crane, 2005) and then marketers realized that consumers concern for the environment and desire for green product did not translate to purchasing behavior (Schram et al, 1995).

The second phase was called "environmental green marketing" where focus shifted to "clean technology". This involved the "designing of innovative new products that take care of pollution and waste. "Sustainable green marketing" was the third and current phase of the concept. Here, green marketing is focused on "Sustainability" and is defined as marketing the needs of the present consumers without compromising the ability of future generation to meet their own needs (Jaspreet et al, 2012). Green marketing is a necessary state for the reconciliation of human needs and nature. But this have not been fully understood and implemented by firms (Kilbourne, 1998). However, Peattie (1994) offers a good starting point by postulating some of the properties of green marketing. These properties which include "holistic and systematic view", an "open-ended time frame", a "global perspective" and the recognition of the intrinsic value of nature is projected to be the bedrock of green marketing.

Approaches to Green Marketing

Mc Daniel and Rylander (1993) identified two broad approaches that a firm might adopt in green marketing. It is either a defensive/ reactionary approach or assertive/aggressive approach.

1. Defensive Approach: Here, companies do the minimal in order to avoid negative consequences

of avoidance. In this case, companies do a lot of maneuvers in order to avoid government tax or penalties. Smith et al., (1990) called this trend “smoke and mirrors” while Kilbonme (1998) calls it “green washing”. Companies that adopt this approach to green marketing are known to have declining market share (Miller, 1990) and witness no significant increase in market acceptance (McDaniel & Rylander, 1993).

2. **Assertive/Aggressive strategy/approach:** This is a green marketing approach which responds to the demands of the market instead of regulations (McDaniel & Rylander, 1993). Firms that adopt this approach are known to be consumer oriented and profit driven (Wells, 1990). The firm in this approach makes the “first move” in the market and enjoys the “first mover advantage” (FMA) in solving environmental problems. Unlike the bandwagon trend of defensive approach provides the best opportunity for sustainable competitive advantage to the company. The image would be that of a sincere environmental activist (McDaniel & Rylander, 1993) which is a competitive advantage.

Challenges that obstruct the adoption of green marketing

Since the year 2000, green marketing has made tremendous growth in western economics (Ottoman et al,2006). More so, the trend is also being imbedded by emerging markets in Asia and South America (Mushura & Sharma, 2010; Lee, 2008). “Going green” is a force that has spread throughout the world. In Africa and Nigeria in particular, the issue of green marketing is still undergoing metamorphosis. There exist a lot of challenges that confront the adoption of green marketing in Nigeria. They are:

1. Regulatory Measures

This is a dimension of CSR and it is one of the reasons firms hold unto green marketing (Carroll, 1991), firms are by law expected to be legally “upright” and it is such a firm that is in a privileged position to invest in new technologies that can aid green marketing. However, a firm that cannot keep up to the regulatory measures invariably goes under (Fernandez-Allies &Caradrado-Marques, 2012).

This is a challenge in the Nigerian business landscape.

2. Lack of Infrastructural Support by Local Authorities

Only a handful of firms are informed of government support in the provision of laws and subsidies that encourages adoption of CSR (Cha 2008; Tzschentke, Kark & Lynch, 2002).

3. Need for Standardization

Only 5% of marketing messages from companies are actually true (Chan, 2008). There is a need for standard quality control board to be set up. The board would be in charge of certifying claims of the organic nature of product that meets the going green requirement.

4. New Concept

It is still a new concept to the masses (Gbodeyan&Omolekan 2015). The consumer need to be educated, enlightened and made to be aware of the threat posed by some of his actions or inactions on the sustainability of the earth. This venture is typically time consuming and firms run away from such responsibility.

5. Avoiding Green Myopia

Companies lose sight of their primary role in business which is customer satisfaction in pursuit of the noble objective of green marketing. If a product is green and does not meet customer satisfaction; it is yet to be a product. Amongst other hindrances to green marketing is the adoption of customer cynicism about green product claims, companies’ intentions and practice distortion is the major reason for its failure (Mendleson&Polonsky, 1995; Peattie & Crane, 2005; Wong et al 2006). Peattie and Crane (2005) identified five marketing practice that could lead to the failure of green marketing. They are:

- **Green spinning:** a reactive approach to green marketing that uses the public relations to deny or

discredit public criticism against a company practice.

- Green selling: an opportunistic approach to green marketing that adds some green claims to existing products with the intention of boasting sales;
- Green harvesting: this occurs when a company becomes enthusiastic about the environment only when “greening” would result in cost savings.
- Entrepreneur marketing: this is the development of “innovative” green products without really understanding customers’ needs and
- Compliance marketing: this occurs when companies promote their green credentials by complying with expected environment legislation without taking initiative to go beyond responding to regulations.

Arguments Regarding Green Marketing & Corporate Social Responsibility Schools of Thought There exist divergent views on the subject matter of CSR. These views can be classified into two schools. The first school suggest “economic performance” while the second school of thought is well embedded on the company moral obligation. The first school of thought is of the opinion that economic performance through the provision of value to society and maximization of organization output (profit) (Bateman& Snell, 1991) is the organizations primary social responsibility. Failure to deliver this primary obligation of the organization will put the organization in a position where she cannot satisfy the society, which could have led to growth and development in the society. Based on the utilitarian theory, this school of thought holds that organization is a part of the economic system and a need for CSR is a need for economic responsibility (Sechi, 2007; Ismali, 2009). This school sees CSR as a form of rules and regulations which are formed to assuage the feelings of the society. In the long run, it is felt that such regulations as CSR will threaten profit maximization and stakeholders’ wellbeing (Armstrong, 1971). They believe that CSR is, but mere window dressing aimed at pre-empting government role as watchdogs and could likely distract business from their basic economic role

The principle of corporate governance is the basis on which the supporters of the second school of thought drew their inspiration. The principle guiding this school of thought states that firms may take into account ethical considerations that are reasonably regarded as appropriate to the responsible conduct of business (Farrell & Fraedrich, 1977) as ethical actions are not considered optional but mandatory (Pastor, 1991). This school argues that organizations are natural members of the society and as such are expected by obligation to be responsibly involved in the community and environmental growth as well as development programmes that would sustain the earth (Bateman & Snell, 1991). Based on instrumental theory, which perceives social activities as tools for marketing to attain economic objectives, the theory supports the engagement of organization in voluntary programmes so that the firm would be perceived by society as being socially responsible and be preferred as such (Ismail, 2009; Jamali&Mirshak, 2007; Wood, 2010).

Empirically, Russo and Fouts (1999) discovered that there is a positive relationship between environmental performance and company profitability. In a later study, Brammer et al, 2012) opines that companies engaging in CSR as one of the ways for increasing a firms’ performance is in bad taste. Matten and Moon (2008) support this assertion that most companies in Japan and Western Europe do not engage in CSR for economic responsibility (that is, profit maximization), but see ethical and social responsibility as reasons to engage in CSR. This line of thought is supported by Carroll (1991) and Visser (2008). Kilbourn (1998) opines that the state of green marketing in the business world involve companies getting involved in green marketing as commendable activities which are primarily managerial strategies and are not targeted toward environmental sustainability. It is argued that green marketing activities fall short expectation since it involves the “greening” of the diverse aspect of traditional marketing.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the social exchange theory. The social theory is founded on the basis of cost and reward system; in other words, cost and reward comparisons drive human decisions and behavior. The image an organization project to the public is by a large extent determined by its level of social exchange with the society. The society should be able to benefit from the organization and vice versa. Kotler & Zaltman (1971) proposed allowing organizations solve societal problems. According to them, an organization can only boast when she is able to solve societal problems in areas where she holds herself as competent. From this assertion, the society should be able to have a good exchange with the organization in which she hosts in her locality. These exchanges would serve as a reward for her sacrifices in accommodating and tolerating (to an extent) the negative effect of hosting the organization. The presence of the organization in the society causes some level of degradation in the environment which in turn affects the livelihood of man who depends on the environment for daily bread. Corporate social responsibility is one of the rewards that must be enjoyed by the society and this is often times manifested by developing programmes that target the sustainability of the environment.

In summary, the social exchange theory means that:

- People are motivated to give up something of value (cost) in order to achieve something of equal value (reward) in a social setting,
- Rewards are usually greater than costs and so, people tend to seek reward more often irrespective of the cost
- Exchange means to trade something of value (costs) for something required (reward)
- Reward is made up of both positive and negative outcomes. The positive outcome is profit which should be greater than the negative outcome (costs) which should be less in comparison to the reward.

Methodology

The study adopted an exploratory research design vis-à-vis the qualitative research approach. This approach enables the researcher to analyze the rate at which companies' carryout their corporate social responsibility programmes through the adoption of green marketing strategy. In-depth interviews were used to gather information from the companies' representative. The population comprises of managers and owners of businesses in Nigeria. A sample was taken from each of the different categories of businesses under study (that is, multi-national, indigenous and small-scale business). Efforts were made to grasp information gathered from the respondents. Data collection occurred in the form of an open-ended question. The semi-structured in-depth interview questions were used to give the interviewees the opportunity to talk freely about their company's CSR programmes and the rate of green marketing adoption in the company.

Results

This section shows the results of the empirical data collected from the conducted qualitative interviews. Data collected with the semi-structured questionnaire were content analyzed to draw out the pattern from the respondents' responses. Respondents were asked to indicate the type of CSR programmes their companies engage in. The pattern of their responses indicates that the company has CSR programmes targeting infrastructure, education, and empowerment.

For the multi-national company, the CSR programmes they engage in include:

- Building of classroom blocks
- Youth and women empowerment
- Construction of boreholes to both host communities and other plans.

We regularly embark on the drilling of boreholes and construction of classrooms in our host community and any other community where there is a lack of such amenities (Respondent 2//5/23).

For the indigenous company, emphasis is laid on alleviating the financial burden of the host community through employing some of the indigenous population. Other community development projects include:

- Building of town halls and boreholes,
- Awarding scholarship to students of the host community

We see it as a duty to help our host community in lifting some financial burdens from their shoulders. After all, performing such task would improve the level of comfort we enjoy in the community (Respondent, 2/5/23)

For the small-scale business which is a sole proprietorship, CSR programmes are presented in the form of charity. We give the much that we can back to the society. We do not expect to gain added patronage from this gesture and we cannot easily fathom the percentage of our sales that increased as a result of our CSR programmes (Respondent, 2/5/23)

Respondents were asked to indicate the reasons behind their corporate social responsibility programmes. CSR means different things to different folks. The information gotten from the content analysis shows varying degrees of reasons of why each company engages in CSR; for the multi-national company, the reason behind CSR is to help people from their organization's success. In the case of the indigenous company, CSR is a way of ensuring peace and stability with the host community and finally, CSR for the small scale business owner is a way of offering charity to the society. In terms of the level of compliance of companies to the adoption of green marketing strategy, the multi-national company has made plans for a gradual migration from the use of gasoline to solar for power generation.

We are concerned about the environment, in that case, we have taken some concrete steps to develop plans that would ensure the gradual migration to renewable energy (Respondent, 2/5/23).

On the other hand, the indigenous company is still grappling with complying with government regulation of less emission into the atmosphere.

We try to adhere to some of the principles of green marketing. For instance, our product packaging is in line with globally accepted best practices. However, other areas such as emission and the use of renewable energy is a trend that we are gradually moving into (Respondent, 2/5/23)

The small-scale business does not have the capacity for green marketing and has not adopted it.

We are still small but growing. We currently do not have the capacity to embark on green marketing (Respondent, 2/5/23).

Summary of Findings

1. Multi-national companies in Nigeria practice corporate social responsibility through provision of infrastructure such as boreholes and block of classrooms as well as women and youth empowerment
2. Indigenous companies are more prone to provide those things that resonate with the need of the host community where it is situated. Programmes they embark on include, offering employment to indigenes of the host community, community development programmes such as building of town halls and boreholes.
3. Small scale businesses also offer CSR to society but in a very small manner. They often regard it as charity.
4. The rationale behind CSR includes helping the society, ensuring peace and stability as well as charity.
5. Multi-nationals are assertive in their approach to green marketing adoption. This could be due to their global spread and the heaviness of their pockets. On the other hand, indigenous companies are defensive in their approach of green marketing approach. This is due to the fact that they do not have the financial capacity to embark on it but would rather handle the issues as they arise

Conclusion

This study set out to examine existing literature on CSR and green marketing and its subsequent adoption in the Nigeria business world. An examination of literature shows that the practice of CSR in general and green marketing in Nigeria is still at its infant stage. Literature also revealed that CSR is defined in line with the peculiar challenges confronting Nigeria. Currently, Nigeria faces a multitude of socio-economic challenges that are based on the basic needs of the citizenry. Ideals of green marketing is still novel because the average Nigerian consumer battles for how to meet physiological needs such as feeding, clothing and shelter and trappings of safety needs such as environmental sustainability might still be farfetched to the average Nigeria. The indigenous companies in Nigeria are likely to engage in defensive approach to green marketing that is, engage in minimal efforts to stay a step ahead of government regulations. Similarly, the practice of green marketing in Nigeria is still largely unknown.

Recommendations

1. There are no rewards for good behavior. However, there should be an incentive for people who comply with green marketing principles such as giving points to people who dispose waste properly.
2. Government should set up a trust fund for companies (especially, small scale business) to use in developing and adopting green marketing strategy.
3. The study also recommends increased creation of awareness on adoption of green marketing strategies as a means of managing the environmental challenges which continues to hunt the different parts of the country.
4. Organization should develop CSR programmes and packages based on precedence. This precedence should target the community, internal business government relation as well as marketing reach. Although, there are programmes that are target at the aforementioned areas, there is a need for these programmes to have local content in order to meet the needs of the indigenous populace.

References

- Adi, A.B.C (2006). The Moral Economy and the Possibility of Accumulation in Africa. How the IFIs can help West Africa Review.
- Amaeshi, K.M and Adi, A.B.C. (2006). Reconstructing the Corporate Social Responsibility Construct in Utlish, Business Ethics: A European Review.
- Amaeshi, K.M., Adi, A.B.C., Ogbechie, C. and Amao, O.O (2006). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Nigeria: Western Mimicry or indigenous practices, ICCSR Research Paper Series, 39.
- Bateman, T.S., and Snell, A.S. (1999). Management: Building Competitive Advantage (4th edition), New York: Irwin Mc Graw-Hill.
- Baucus, M. and Baucus, D. (1997). Paying the Piper: An Empirical Examination of Longer Term Financial Consequences of Illegal Corporate Behavior, Academy of Management Journal, 40 (1): 129-151.
- Carroll, A.B. (1991). The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the Moral Management of Organizational Stakeholders, Business Horizons 43 (4): 39-48.
- Carroll, A.B. (2004). Managing Ethically with Global Stakeholders: A Present and Future Challenge, Academy of Management Executive, 18(2):114-119.

- Chan, E.S. (2008). Barriers to EMS in the Hotel Industry, *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 27 (2): 187-196. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2007.07.011>.
- Chan, R.Y.K. (2004). consumer responses to environmental advertising in China, *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 22(4): 427-437. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02634500410542789>.
- DhirajS.(2014) Green Marketing, Postgraduate Power Point Lecture note, Green Marketing 13101240001-phapp01.
- Chapple, W. and Moon, J. (2005). Responsibility (CSR) in Asia: A Seven-Country Study of CSR website Reporting. *Business & Society*, 44(4): 415-439.
- Elkington, J. (1989), "Why it pays to be Green", *Financial Times*, October 14.
- Elkington, J. (1989), "Power of the consumer to buy a better world" *observer*, September 29
- Feldman, L. (1971), "Societal adaption: A new challenge for marketing", *Journal of Marketing* 37 (3): 54-60.
- Ferrell, O.C. and Fraedrich, J.(1997). *Business Ethics: Ethical Decision Making*,
- Fougere, M., Solitander, N. (2009). Against Corporate Responsibility: Critical reflections on Thinking, practice, Content and consequences. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 16(4):217-227. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/csr.204>
- Gbadeyan, R.A & Omolekan, O.. J. (2015). Relevance of green marketing on environmental degradation: an empirical study of consumers of green products in Benin city Nigeria, *Research Journal of University of Mauritius*, 21.
- Huxley, A. (1968), "The Politics of Ecology", In: *The Triple Revolution*. (Eds.) Perruccu, R. & Pilisuk. Boston: Little Brown.
- Hsieh, N.H. (2009). Corporate Social Responsibility and the Priority of Shareholders, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 88:553-560. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10551-009-0314-7>.
- Hsieh, Y.C.J. (2012). Hotel companies environmental policies and practices: a content analysis of their web pages. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 24(1): 97-121. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/095961112>
- Ismail, M. (2009) Corporate social responsibility and its role in community development: an international perspective, *the Journal of International Social Research*, 2 (9): 200-209.
- Jamali, D. (2008). A Stakeholder Approach to Corporate Social Responsibility: a Fresh Perspective into Theory and Practice, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 82 (1):213-231. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10551-007-9572-www.ccsenet.org/ass> *Asian Social Science* 9(17)

Jamali, D., & Mirshak, R. (2007). Corporate social responsibility (CSR): theory and practice in a developing country context. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 72 (3): 243-262. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10551-006-9168-4>.

Jaspreet, S., Jatin, M., Jogesh, P. & Jupinder, K. (2012) Green Marketing, Class Presentation on Green marketing 49659549-green-marketing-121007044818-phpapp02.

Kilbourne, W.E. (1998) Green Marketing: A Theoretical Perspective, *Journal of Marketing Management*, 14 (6):641-655, DOI:10.1362/026725798784867743

Kotler, P and Levy, S. (1969), "Broadening the Concept of Marketing", *Journal of Marketing* 33(1): 10-15.

Kotler, P. and Zaltman, G. (1971), "Social marketing: An approach to planned social change", *Journal of Marketing*, 35 (3): 3-12.

Lee, K. (2008). Opportunities for green marketing: young consumers, *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 26(6):573-586. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02634500810902839>.

Matten, D., & Moon, J. (2008). "Implicit" and "explicit" CSR: a conceptual framework for a comprehensive understanding of corporate social responsibility. *Academy of Management Review* 33(2): 404-424, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMR.2008.31193458>.

Mc Daniel, S.W. & Rylander, D.H., (1993). Strategic Green Marketing, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 10 (5): 410

Mc Williams, A. & Siegel, D. (2001). Corporate Social Responsibility: A Theory of the Firm Perspective, *Academy of Management Review*, 26 (1): 7-127.

Menon, A and Menon, A. (1997). Environmental Marketing Strategy: The Emergence of Corporate Environmentalism marketing strategy, *Journal of Marketing*, January, 51-67.

Mishra, P. & Sharama, P. (2010) Green marketing in India Emerging Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Engineering Science and Management Education*, 3, PP 9-14

Moon, J. (2002). Corporate Social Responsibility: An Overview, *International Directory of Corporate Philanthropy* (pp.3-14) London: Europe.

Oko, A.E.N. and Agbonifoh, B.A. (2014). Corporate Social Responsibility in Nigeria: a Study of the Petroleum Industry and the Niger Delta Area, *IRSSH Journal* 6(2): 214-238, www.irssh.com

Orpen, C. (2000). The Attitudes of United State of America Managers to Corporate Social Responsibility, *Journal of Business Ethics* 6(2): 89-96.

O'Toole, J. (1991). Doing well by Doing Good: The Business Enterprise Trust Awards, *California Management Review*, Spring, 9-24.

- Ottman, J.A. (1990), Environmental Concerns Open Markets for New Products, *Marketing News*, 19 March, p.21.
- Peattie, K. (2001), "Golden Goose or Wild Goose? The Hunt for the Green Consumer, *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 10 (4):187-99.
- Peattie, K. and Crane, A. (2005), Green Marketing: Legend, Myth, Farce or Prophecy? *Qualitative Market Research*, 8(4)357-70.
- Polonsky, M.J. (2011). Transformative green marketing: Impediments and opportunities. *Journal of Business Research*, 64 (12): 1311-1310, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.01.016>.
- Prothero, A. (1990) Green Consumerism and the Societal Marketing Strategies for the 1990's *Journal of Marketing Management*, 6 (2): 87-103, DOI: 10.1080/0267257X.1990.9964119.
- Punitha, S., & Rasdi, M.R. (2013). Corporate Social Responsibility: Adoption of Green Marketing in the Hotel Industry, *Journal of Asian Social Sciences*, Vol.9 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ass.v9n17p79>.
- Russo, M. and Fouts, P., (1997). A Resource-based Perspective on Corporate Environmental performance and Profitability, *Academy of Management Journal*, 40:118-137.
- Secchi, D. (2007). Utilitarian, Managerial and Relational Theories of Corporate Social Responsibility. *International Journal Management Reviews*, 9 (4): 347-373. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.14682370.2007.00215.x>.
- Simbrisio, C. Mntongi, C. & Thabani, N (2021), Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Corporate Image, *International Research Journal of Innovation in Engineering and Technology*, 5(3), 428-436
- Tzschentke, N.A., Kirk, D., & Lynch, P.A. (2008). Going Green: Decisional Factors in Small Hospitality Operations. *International Journal of Hospitality management*, 27 (1), 126-133. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2007.07.010>.
- Visser, W. (2006). Revisiting Carrolls CSR Pyramid in R. Pedersen and Huniche, M. (Eds), *Corporate Citizenship in Developing Countries*, The Copenhagen Centre.